

Health care issues in Nigeria

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Abstract

Health care in Sub-Saharan Africa is among the least effective in the world. Moreover, it is not readily available for ordinary Nigerians. Only the elite enjoy better living conditions and better health. Thanks to numerous humanitarian aids, over the last sixty years, a slight progress in combating diseases and in care over children and mothers can be observed. Despite this change, the difference in life expectancy between the wealthy and the poor remains immense. The main causes of death in the Sub-Saharan region include HIV/AIDS, malaria, respiratory diseases, diarrhoea, perioperative complications, and many other diseases.

Keywords: Nigeria, health care, Africa

Introduction

Sub-Saharan Africa is a region dominated by countries characterized by the lowest indices of social development. The area consists of 48 countries, including 33 with the lowest Human Development Index. The region faces numerous natural disasters, as well as armed conflicts and is stricken by suffering, hunger and diseases [1]. According to the data of the World Tourism Organization (WTO), the number of travellers has doubled over the last decade. Some travel for professional reasons, but the majority comes as tourists in search of attractive holiday spots [2]. Unfortunately, not everybody is aware that in these tropical countries, with the climate so different from the Polish one, infections with tropical diseases are a very real issue [3].

Africa is a continent of 53 countries and a rich blend of indigenous peoples, cultures, economy and history. It is the second biggest continent in the world. Two-thirds of Sub-Saharan Africa counties are the poorest worldwide. In 31 from 53 of African countries, the food production is dropping and it is estimated that 200 million Africans are starving [4].

The list of 48 poorest countries in the world includes 35 African countries. From among 15 countries with the highest death rates among children, 14 are located in Sub-Saharan Africa [5].

In Sub-Saharan Africa, 52% of people have no access to clean water, 62% do not have their own sanitary facilities and 50 million of preschool children suffer from malnutrition. The African health care faces serious shortage of medical personnel, diagnostic equipment and drugs; healthcare institutions have problems with lack of electricity and clean water [6].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there should be 1 physician per every 5000 people, whereas in Africa 16 doctors are to care for 100 thousand inhabitants. In many countries, e.g. in Malawi, there is only 1 doctor per 100 thousand persons. Availability of highly qualified specialist is drastically low, e.g. at a very

high rate of skin diseases, which are also side effects of HIV infections, 1 dermatologist is to care for 3-4 million people. For every 100 thousand people, there are approximately 150 of nurses and midwives [1].

Thanks to numerous humanitarian aids, over the last sixty years, a slight progress in combating diseases and in care over children and mothers can be observed. Health care in Africa is provided on a basic level and three hospital levels: local (county, district), regional (province, state) and national (highly specialist university hospitals, research and development centres) [1, 7].

Basic health care is free, whereas any help provided by non-profit organizations or private health centres has to be paid for [1].

Outpatient clinics and small health centres provide medical consultations, diagnostics and routine treatment. In order to see a specialist, a referral is needed [6, 7].

Health crisis in Africa results from poverty, malnutrition, hunger, tropical weather conditions, low hygiene standards (open latrines), appalling sanitary and housing conditions, lack of sewerage systems, shortages of clear washing/drinking water (people drink water from unprotected tanks used also by cattle, contaminated with human and animal faeces), polluted environment, limited access to electricity and basic health care [6, 7].

Moreover, the crisis is enhanced by drugs and alcohol, the consumption of which increases (drugs in the cities and alcohol in the country) [5].

Other factors include: overuse of mass vaccinations, intensive pharmacological immunization, development of a black market of prohibited, falsified, expired or poor-quality medicines, overconsumption of antibiotics and other drugs in self-treatment, promotion of dangerous contraceptives often without any doctor's supervision, house abortions, introduction of invasive medicine (injections, operations, transfusions) under insufficient hygiene conditions, poor medical infrastructure, lack of qualified personnel [1].

It is estimated that 80% of disposable syringes in Africa is reused. Approximately 2 to 3 million of Africans suffer from tuberculosis and several hundred thousand die of it every year [1, 8]. Moreover, since the 1980s, the number of people suffering from malaria is increasingly high [1, 5, 7].

According to some statistics, the average incidence of diseases has increased four times since the 1980s, and in some regions – even eleven times. The most serious health threats in Africa include tuberculosis, malaria, diarrhoea, dysentery, coma, leprosy, cholera, anaemia, acute respiratory infections, viral, bacterial and parasitic infections, sexually transmitted diseases, paediatric diseases [1, 5, 7, 8].

Unfortunately, due to focusing on „War with AIDS in Africa”, the international public opinion and the mass media do not devote as much attention to these diseases as they deserve [5].

Nigeria is the biggest country in Africa and the 7th largest oil exporter in the world [9]. The Federal Republic of Nigeria is located in West Africa by the Gulf of Guinea. The worst plagues of Nigeria include malaria, HIV infection, tuberculosis and famine. Nigeria has the population of 160-170 million people; 434 ethnic groups speak 395 different languages. The North is inhabited by Hausa and Fulani tribes, the South by Yoruba and Ibo people. Over 92% of Nigerians live on less than 2 dollars a day [9].

Millions of people in Africa live in extreme poverty. Access to health care is very limited; possible almost only in big cities. The level of medical and nursing care services, which are very costly, is a long way from meeting the world standards. A doctor's visit costs around 100 USD, including blood tests for malaria [10, 11].

A day in hospital is 100-250 USD. Doctors are unable to use modern diagnostic methods or perform more advanced laboratory tests. In West Africa, very poor quality of medical services is a serious problem. In Abuja, the capital city of Nigeria, not a single health institution complies even with minimum European standards [11].

Only one clinic, employing European doctors and nurses, has obsolete equipment and performs only basic laboratory tests.

The most common infections in Nigeria include typhus, salmonella, jaundice, HIV, polio, cholera, meningococcal meningitis, malaria and other infectious diseases [9, 11].

Due to poor healthcare, ineffective drugs and lack of appropriate diagnostic methods, the risk of serious infections and complications is very high. Pharmacies obtain most of the drugs from sources not controlled by national institutions [11, 12]. Drugs are stored improperly – most pharmacies lack 24-hour air conditioning and power outages are frequent [11].

Physicians and nurses themselves have doubts as to the quality of the drugs they administer. In the Federal Republic of Nigeria, doctoral and nursing care is unsatisfactory. Even in cases of common ailments, the

approved drugs are hard to get and hospital care standards are very low [11].

Summary

A trip to Nigeria, a tropical region, should be carefully considered and planned. The prophylactic recommendations ought to include: information on the region and its environment, weather and climate conditions depending on the season of the year, character and length of stay, accommodation conditions (hotel, bungalow, tent, access to running water, etc.), age of the traveller and coexisting diseases as well as possible local threats that are often difficult to envisage [13, 14, 15]. The abovementioned actions limit the trip-related risks though do not eliminate them completely.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.